

ISic1096

I.Sicily inscription 1096

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

stone

Object

base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Marsala

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140576

1. [—]IPες [Λ]ιλ[υβ]α [ῖται — —]
2. [M(ἄρκον)] ΟὐαλέριοΟν ²⁶Οὐαλέριον²⁶ Δι[ογνή]-
3. [το]υ [M]η[γ]αν(—) υῖὸν [Χόρ]-
4. [τ]ωνα ε[ὺ]ερ[γ]έταν.
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492717

EDCS 39102251

PHI 140576

Bibliography

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-22): ISic1096. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4385475>